

*Extending Anthophila research through
image and trait digitization (Big-Bee) annual
cumulative report*

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Year 3: September 01, 2023 - August 31, 2024

Accomplishments:

Major Project Goals:

The goal of Big-Bee is to expand bee research through the digitization of bee traits and images. To accomplish this goal, we will create over 1.2M images of over 5K bee species and share these images via the Bee Library and through published curated datasets. These goals will be accomplished using many methods, including developing novel Notes from Nature measurement tools.

The digitization goals of Big-Bee are (Table 1):

1. 572,813 newly digitized specimens of 5,509 target taxa. The focus is on complete digitization, which includes georeferencing and images with both specimens and labels.
2. ca. 109,000 high-resolution, multifocal stacked Exemplar and Diagnostic images, including focal taxa and bee parasites.
3. 10,300 3D Image Suites for 3D image reconstruction.
4. Score Morphological Traits from images, including Body Size, Hair Color, and Hairiness.
5. Score Life History Traits from literature, including Phenology, Nesting Biology, Sociality, and Biotic Associations (Floral Specialization, Parasites, and Pathogens).

Data and images will be discoverable via iDigBio, GBIF, Bee Library (Symbiota database), and as published curated datasets.

Digitizing institution	Digitized specimens	Focus-stacked images	3D image suites	Additional Images
Arizona State University (ASUHC)	10,000	0	0	
California Academy of Sciences (CAS)	142,325	5,474	500	
Florida State Collection of Arthropods (FSCA)	90,495	5,294	500	
Harvard University (MCZ)	52,324	6,492	500	
Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)	2000	0	0	2,000 (microCT)
Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County (LACM)	72,681	6,543	500	
San Diego Natural History Museum (SDMC)	14,224	797	3,000	

Digitizing institution	Digitized specimens	Focus-stacked images	3D image suites	Additional Images
University of California-Berkeley (EMEC)	69,297	9,892	100	
University of California, Santa Barbara (UCSB)	8,697	5,092	4,000	
University of Colorado (UCMC)	62,677	10,160	100	
University of Kansas (SEMC)	9,495	28,185	100	
University of Michigan Museum of Zoology (UMMZ)	27,815	15,198	500	
University of New Hampshire Collection of Insects and Arthropods (UNHC)	6,783	12850	500	1,000 (CLSM)
USGS Native Bee Inventory and Monitoring Lab (USGS BIML)	4000	4,000	0	
Total:	572,813	109,977	10,300	3,000

Table 1: Digitization goals outlining the 572K specimens to be published and digitized using multiple imaging modalities; 109K high-resolution, focal stacked exemplar and diagnostic images; 10,300 3D image suites consisting of ~64 focal stacked images per suite; and 3,000 CT or CLSM images. Grey highlighted rows are non-funded partners.

Biodiversity Informatics goals are:

1. Create the Bee Library as a Symbiota portal dedicated to bees and bee traits;
 - a. expand Symbiota’s ability to link to external resources, including the ability to link to: externally managed literature (via Weblink DOI), observations (e.g., iNaturalist), other image datasets (e.g., CT, CLSM, and 3D models held outside of ASU), and other related specimens;
 - b. investigate options for sharing Image View (e.g., dorsal, ventral) as a property in Audubon Core in Symbiota;
 - c. extend the Symbiota Trait Management Tools developed by the CAP TCN to manage bee traits from both literature and specimen sources;
 - d. extend the image and dataset search capabilities in Symbiota based on locality, taxon, and view; and
 - e. Add bee observation collections.

2. Publish versioned datasets of the textual trait data and “training datasets” of image data as products;
3. Establish connections between Bee-Bee Global Biotic Interactions, iDigBio, and GBIF;
4. Investigate computer vision for traits and improved methods for 3D image reconstruction;
5. Integrate additional bee data from network collections, monitoring programs, and federal collections (e.g., USGS, USDA, Smithsonian) via established IPTs or spreadsheet uploads; and
6. Participate in the OpenTraits Network.

Outreach, workforce training, and broader impact goals:

1. Create a Research Advisory Board;
2. Provide digitization resources for all global bee collections, including the ability to digitize specimens through the Big-Bee Symbiota portal and support from a portal data manager to help train and facilitate the upload and data sharing;
3. Participate fully with the Bee Monitoring USDA-RCN;
4. Create a science-themed radio program about bees;
5. Contribute lesson plans to BLUE (Biodiversity Literacy for Undergraduate Education);
6. Continue efforts to recruit students from underrepresented groups;
7. Provide opportunities for all participants to advance skills in biodiversity information science, bee identification, high-resolution imaging, museum curation, and outreach.
 - a. 3D and high-resolution imaging provided by Mark Smith, owner and developer of Macroscopic Solutions, LLC;
 - b. data curation and workflows using the Symbiota portal, including georeferencing, data management, trait annotation, and Bee Library dataset creation;
 - c. annotating and defining traits in the Bee Library;
 - d. creating a citizen science bee inventory using the Bee Library to create identification tools.
 - e. online bee morphology and Bee Library workshops will be developed in years two and three of the project. The first will focus on bee male genitalia and it will include how to prepare specimens and use the Bee Library for identification by comparing images to dissected specimens. In year three, a two-day virtual workshop on bee identification and trait determination will train novel bee researchers on how best to use the Bee Library to inform their identification efforts.
 - f. two undergraduate computer science projects will be developed by a Postdoctoral Researcher at UCSB for incorporation into the recently funded NSF “HDR DSC: Collaborative Research: Central Coast Data Science Partnership: Training a New Generation of Data Scientists” initiative.

Accomplishments Under These Goals:

Continuing Project: All 13 institutions funded by the grant continued to be engaged and successfully contributing to the project in 2023/24 reporting period (UNHC, UMMZI, UCSB,

FSCA, LACM, UNR, SEMC, SDMC, UCMC, CAS, EMEC, ASUHIC, MCZ - see participant list at end of document for institution details). Many partners are planning to submit a request for no cost extension (NCE). UNR has finished their funding and will not be requesting a NCE.

Digitization Workflows: All partner institutions continue digitizing specimens with images of labels. UCSB & UNHC have already exceeded their original goals for Specimen with Label digitization. UCMC, UMMZI, EMEC and MCZ are over 50% toward their goal. Year 3 continued to focus on 3D digitization with an ongoing **3D Modeling Short Course** led by Mark Smith, Macroscopic Solutions. Macroscopic Solutions actively manages two channels found publicly on the Big-Bee's support network hosted by Slack (https://join.slack.com/t/big-beeworkspace/shared_invite/zt-1yfgtbfa9-bbFQsqMf9Od9FWPrO3FWag). In response to support requests via Slack and during regular office hours (Wed 4 PM EST), a series of presentations and instructional videos have been produced. A total of 16 help and tutorial videos were created and shared on the Macroscopic Solutions YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@macropod/videos>).

Multiple institutions created online protocols for 2D, 3D and modeling workflows during this period. Including:

1. Smith, C., Reyes, S., Ryan, K. A., Smith, M., Deer, E., Sanchez, E., Sheccid, R. T., Kung, G.-A., Carper, A. L., & Seltmann, K. (2024). UCSB's 3D imaging and modeling protocol. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10594883>
2. Sanchez, E., Rivas Trasvina, S., & Smith, C. (2024). Protocol for adding scale bar and measuring bee volume from 3d models (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10688931>

Digitization: 409,998 images have been captured for Big-Bee (September 15, 2021 - July 10, 2024). This is up from **220,779** reported in 2023 (**64,454** reported the first year).

Label with Specimen Image Digitization: Big-Bee will image, transcribe, and georeference **572,813** new specimens as part of the project. We have completed approximately **52%** of our Label with Specimen Image Digitization goals (Figure 1; Table 2). Georeferenced numbers are likely lower than reality because not all institutions track the difference between transcription and georeferenced. Transcription and Georeferencing are expected to be behind specimen imaging as our workflow first involves imaging the specimen with the label, following transcription of data from the images. Diagnostic Images, and **612** specimens were imaged for 3D imaging (including 153 microCT images). **76,845** multifocal stacked, high resolution images were generated in the process. These are multi-stacked images photographed with the Macropod Pro imaging system (Table 3).

Figure 1: Label with Specimen digitization progress. Label with Specimen images are newly digitized specimens that need imaging, transcription of data to databases, and georeferencing.

	Complete 2023	Complete 2024	Remaining
Specimen Images	186,696	110,543	275,574
Transcribed	53,699	15,651	503,463
Georeferenced	39,272	13,421	520,120

Table 2: Label with Specimen digitization progress.

	Complete 2023	Complete 2024	Remaining
Exemplar & Diagnostic Images	23,330	12,431	74,216
3D imaged specimens	99	360	9,841
3D image stacks	10,713	66,132	629,824
CLSM/CT	40	113	2,847

Table 3: High resolution imaging progress.

Digitization Progress Per Institution: The details for each institution's progress are listed in Table 4. Yellow cells indicate digitization goals over 50% complete. Green indicates completed or over goal. Blank indicates that the institution is not imaging this type of image (Table 4). While our digitization has been very successful a few institutions had setbacks this year. UCMC had a major water leak that stopped imaging in the collections for most of 2024. LACM's collection underwent significant renovations that stopped image production for several months. FSCA/SDMC lost critical employees and had to hire/retrain someone new. See individual collaborator reports for more details about these setbacks and how each institution is planning to stay on target.

Overall, doing high resolution imaging and 3D imaging is more time consuming than estimated, however, the images we are creating are of great research value (see significant products, below).

	UNHC	UCSB	FSCA	SEMC	SDMC	UCMC	UMMZI	CAS	EMEC	LACM	ASUHIC	MCZ
Label with Specimen Images	700	6,594	20,527	0	3,427	54,223	54,223	44,363	48,395	31,697	3,499	29,591
New specimen data transcribed	0	5,322	20,257	0	1,348	1,442	2,393	2,873	5,640	687	0	29,388
New specimens georeferenced	0	5,386	18,412	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	28,895
Focus-stacked exemplar images	3,272	2,106	1,152	12,222	488	1,325	3,641	1,315	3,024	320	2,149	3,425
Focus-stacked diagnostic images	405	917										
Number of images for 3D suites	0	13,908	0	0	15,531	12,999	0	0	0	9,400	0	25,007
3D specimens	0	108	0	0	71	104	0	0	0	88	0	88
microCT/CLSM	153	0										
Total images	4,530	23,525	21,679	12,222	19,446	68,547	57,864	45,678	51,419	41,417	5,648	58,023

Table 4: Digitization progress per Institution. Yellow cells indicate digitization goals over 50% complete. Green indicates completed or over goal. Blank indicates that the institution is not imaging this type of image.

Macroscopic Solutions: Mark Smith, founder and CEO of Macroscopic Solutions continues to work with Big-Bee. This collaboration has led to improvement in the 3D imaging technology (see **What is the impact on technology transfer?**) and many online resources about how to do 3D imaging of small objects (See **How have results been disseminated to communities of interest?**, below).

Notes from Nature: To facilitate label transcription and to measure body size, UNR built a custom Notes from Nature project for Big-Bee called the Big-Bee Bonanza. The project includes a designated bee-themed landing page and several pages outlining how community scientists

can get involved in the Big-Bee project. It also includes information about the research goals, project team members, a place to track project statistics, and a forum for online discussion. The Big-Bee Notes from Nature Project currently includes **3** custom workflows to suit the needs of researchers and ensure standardized data outputs. Two of these workflows are focused on the transcription of label information. The third is for measuring bee tegula, a proxy for body size (Figure 2). LACM, UCSB, EMEC, UCMC & CAS have used the project resulting in **65,064** completed subjects (up from **37,126** last year) and **2,986** volunteers (up from **1,756** volunteers last year).

<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/md68135/notes-from-nature-big-bee-bonanza>

Figure 2: Notes from Nature “Field Guide” for how to take body size measurements in bees.

Bee Library Symbiota Portal: The Big-Bee Symbiota portal (Bee Library - <https://library.big-bee.net>) was rapidly launched in the first quarter of the project (October 2021). The portal is currently managed by the Symbiota Support Hub at ASU and will be moving to KU this year (along with the PI and the Symbiota Support Hub).

The Bee Library hosts **3,501,173** occurrence records (up from **2,123,637 last year**) from **61** collections (up from **18 last year**). **88%** of the specimens are georeferenced, **25%** contain images, and **87%** are identified to species (retrieved August 22, 2024). All Big-Bee participants are sharing data with the Bee Library, but the largest boost in participation has come outside of the funded collaborators, demonstrating broad support of the Big-Bee Library portal in the bee community.

1. Continued user support for all project participants and new projects associated with the Bee Library. For example, UCSB and the Bee Library (Symbiota Support Hub) are supporting Jeannie Chari from the College of the Canyons with her funded NSF RCN-UBE project (#2316506). The students are surveying their campuses for bees. PI Seltmann is on the project advisory committee, and their data is being uploaded to the Bee Library. Both Seltmann and the Hub have been guiding project leaders in databasing efforts. This project has **27 faculty mentors** representing **20 community colleges** in both California and Arizona. Collectively, these faculty members are currently mentoring **49 individual students**. Additionally, one faculty member implemented a native Bee CURE for the first time, which an entire class of students participated in. As a second example, PI Seltman and the Hub are also working to integrate datasets from the Texas Native Bee Research Coordination Network, led by Megan O’Connell at the University of Texas at Austin, into the Bee Library, which will continue into the next project year. This collaborating group is especially interested in using the Bee Library as a platform for data publishing to GBIF.
2. Bee Library is now also supporting the iDigBees NSF TCN project with project data aggregation and publication.
3. Bee Library had a highly successful [Portal Advancement Campaign](#) in September 2023 (the results were not included in the last report). The target for this campaign was to 1) bring other bee collections into the Bee Library and 2) provide a publication pipeline for bee monitoring datasets to GBIF. Highlights from the campaign include:
 - Engaging 17 representatives of bee research collections through a series of three virtual meetings (recordings found at <https://symbiota.org/portal-advancement-campaigns/bee-library-portal-campaign/>), 16 (94%) who had not previously participated in the Big-Bee TCN
 - Adding 32 collections and 784,407 specimen occurrences to the Bee Library, including several large datasets from federal bee research labs and 74,349 records with genetic sequence data from the Barcode of Life
 - Increasing the total number of records in the portal with georeferences to 1.15 M records (88% georeferenced in total)
 - Adding 1,128 taxa (including 40 genera and 1,081 species) to the Bee Library’s central taxonomic thesaurus
4. Disseminating new image tagging workflows developed by the Big-Bee TCN via a recorded Symbiota Support Group webinar. Colleen Smith (UC Santa Barbara & Big-Bee TCN) presented methods to 1) make images of specimens easier for people to find and cite in Symbiota, 2) tag different types of specimen images in Symbiota, and 3) package and link sets of images to specimen records using GitHub and Zenodo. Recording: <https://youtu.be/ipSYqwgovVU?si=W3XiV4MuaF38Loyx>
5. Configuring the Bee Library’s Traits module to capture bee Flight Period data (“active” vs. “inactive”).

6. The Symbiota Support Hub continues to send a representative to the regular Big-Bee check-in meetings to provide portal support to this TCN community.

Global Biotic Interactions: Big-Bee is sharing in a single, aligned dataset over **1 million** bee interactions as part of the Global Bee Interaction Dataset. Of these ca. **200K** are coming from Big-Bee institutions. This dataset has been downloaded over 1000 times and is currently being used in several research and conservation based products. For example, the USDA is using the dataset for a use case to expand the PLANTS database to include pollinator-plant interactions.

- Seltmann, K. C., Poelen, J. H., & Global Biotic Interaction Community. (2024). Global Bee Interaction Data (v4.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12639658>

Seltmann and Poelen continue to maintain a data monitoring page at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/bigbee> to review and track the availability of Big-Bee-associated natural history collections. These reviews are linked through shared IPT or Darwin Core archives and involve assessing taxon names, the number of biotic interactions, and data structure. The Discover Life bee name list, widely recognized as the authoritative source, has been integrated by Seltmann & Poelen into *nomer*, the nomenclature handling software for Global Biotic Interactions. This integration makes the list broadly accessible for reuse, allowing collections to verify their names directly against the Discover Life checklist. This effort resulted in two published products: the *nomer* software and a delimited file of the bee species checklist.

- José Augusto Salim, & Jorrit Poelen. (2024). *globalbioticinteractions/nomer: 0.5.13* (0.5.13). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.1145474>
- Seltmann, K., & Poelen, J. (2024). Tab and comma delimited versions of Discover Life bee species guide and world checklist (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Anthophila) (56.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10019874>

What opportunities for training and professional development has the project provided?

A weekly meeting via Zoom continues to be an important part of creating Big-Bee workflows, project organization, and onboarding new participants. The Zoom meetings are very well attended by participants, Symbiota Support Hub staff, project consultants, Macropod Solutions staff, and other project collaborators. The meetings also provided a venue for imaging training by Mark Smith (Macroscopic Solutions). They have, and continue to, provide much-needed open office time for questions.

Big-Bee uses Slack software to enhance communication. We presently have **123** members on Slack, including project PIs, collaborators, Symbiota Support Hub staff, undergraduates, and technicians. Slack is being used for day-to-day project management and training/communication about imaging, Notes from Nature, and other project goals.

Additional training activities were facilitated by the Symbiota Support Hub as part of the aforementioned Portal Advancement Campaign on the topics of data ingestion, data publishing, and research use of the Bee Library data portal.

Macroscopic Solutions actively engages in support channels through email, [macroscopicolutions.com](https://www.youtube.com/@macropod/podcasts) support forum, YouTube and Slack. We have hosted a new podcast series (<https://www.youtube.com/@macropod/podcasts>) where scientists with niche imaging

questions ask Macroscopic Solutions for insight or instructions. The podcast opens their questions up to a larger community to share protocols in an open-source manner. Similarly, our YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@macropod/videos>) and Forum (<https://macroscopicsolutions.com/forum/official-forum/>) serve as hubs for individuals seeking how-to guides and instructions for focus stacking and 3D photogrammetry techniques.

How have results been disseminated to communities of interest?

- A total of **1** student oral presentations, **10** student posters, **11** student research projects, and **9** published scholarly articles this year.
- Big-Bee was mentioned in **9** academic presentations this year.
- Big-Bee was presented or discussed in **36 events** (i.e., open house, collection tours) across the network, with **15,260 attendees**.
- PI Seltmann and Big-Bee partner Erika Tucker (iDigBees) continue to collaborate with Hollis Woodard (USDA Bee Monitoring RCN) in developing a published *Wild Bee Data Standard* to ensure smoother data handling and dissemination of bee data. Publishing data to GBIF and following FAIR data principles is central to this document. The Bee Library is preparing (with support from the Symbiota Support Hub) to accommodate both monitoring (observation) and collection data about bees from multiple research projects.
- Rather than developing independent help resources, Big-Bee continues to help develop the Symbiota Support Hub (<https://symbiota.org/help-resources>) and Macroscopic Solutions help resources for the entire community.
- Big-Bee has created a Zenodo Community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/bigbee/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>) to highlight and archive our resources and datasets.
- Macroscopic Solutions has created open-source PDFs and tutorial videos describing photogrammetric workflows. These videos are accessible on Macroscopic Solutions Youtube channel and website. Since creating this content, Macroscopic Solutions has seen a sharp increase in academic-based subscriptions. (Examples: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXhbJ-JirA3-J7FihjXtUyg> and <https://macroscopicsolutions.com/video-tutorial-big-bee-tcn/>)
- Big-Bee is represented via our websites, GitHub project, and data portals (see Products). The Bee Library Symbiota portal was visited by ca. **11,000** users between September 01, 2023 - August 22, 2024. This is up from **3,281** users last year. The majority of the users (98%) found the Bee Library by direct search.

What do you plan to do during the next reporting period to accomplish the goals?

- During the fourth year of the project, all Big-Bee institutions will continue to focus on reaching their digitization goals, including 3D imaging.

- We will continue to work closely with our partners at the ASU Symbiota Support Hub to expand the use of the Bee Library.
- We will continue Notes from Nature expeditions for body size measurements and label transcriptions.
- Year 4 will continue to focus on trait data, including how to incorporate trait data into the Bee Library Symbiota portal. UCSB postdoctoral researcher Madeline Ostwald will focus on aggregating trait data to include in the portal and as separately published datasets.
- Poelen and Seltmann will continue examining image corpus publication for image datasets, particularly around 3D image models.

Cumulative Products

To date, the project has produced **14** peer-reviewed journal publications, **36** posters and talks, and **21** shared datasets or workshop reports.

Journal Paper:

1. Engel, M.S. (2022) New species of the stingless bee genus *Plebeia* (Hymenoptera: Apidae). *Journal of Melittology* 114: 1–28.
2. Baskauf SJ, Girón Duque JC, Nielsen M, Cobb NS, Singer R, Seltmann KC, Kachian Z, Pérez M, Agosti D, Klompen AML (2023) Implementation Experience Report for Controlled Vocabularies Used with the Audubon Core Terms subjectPart and subjectOrientation. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 7: e94188. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.7.94188>
3. Ostwald, M. M., Thrift, C. N., & Seltmann, K. C. (2023) Phenotypic divergence in an island bee population: Applying geometric morphometrics to discriminate population-level variation in wing venation. *Ecology and Evolution*, 13, e10085. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10085>
4. Engel, M.S. (2023) A new species of *Callomegachile* from Larat, Indonesia (Hymenoptera: Megachilidae). *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine* 159(1): 13–18.
5. G.W. Frankie, S.L. Witt, J.C. Pawelek, B. Faber, R.E. Coville, M.A. Rizzardi, M.H. Chase, J. O'Sullivan, K.C. Seltmann. (2024) Hedgerow Gardens Provide Floral Resources for Diverse Insect Visitors to Avocado Flowers in Southern California," *Journal of the Kansas Entomological Society*, 96(3), 39-67
6. Ostwald, M. M., da Silva, C. R. B., & Seltmann, K. C. (2024). How does climate change impact social bees and bee sociality? *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 00, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.14160>
7. Payne, Helen E., Susan Mazer, and Katja C Seltmann. (2024) Native Bee Habitat Restoration: Key Ecological Considerations from Recent North American Literature. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution* 12: 1358621.
8. Ostwald M.M., Venegas V.A., Seltmann S.C. (2024) Social conditions facilitate water conservation in a solitary bee, *Journal of Insect Science*, 24: 1. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jisesa/ieae001>
9. Engel, MS. (2024). On the classification of sphecodine bees (Hymenoptera: Halictidae). *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine* 160(1): 1–52.

10. Engel, MS. (2023). An illustrated key to Anthophoroides Cockerell & Cockerell, with the description of three new species (Hymenoptera: Apidae). *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine* 159: 147–167.
11. Engel, MS. (2023). A new species of Dioxys Lepeletier & Audinet-Serville from southern Spain, with notes on the classification of Dioxyni (Hymenoptera: Megachilidae). *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine* 159: 175–182.
12. Engel, MS. (2023). Two new species of Cystopsenella Kieffer from Belize and Peru (Hymenoptera: Scolebythidae). *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine* 159: 197–204.

Juried Conference Paper:

13. Seltmann KC, Allen J, Brown BV, Carper A, Engel MS, Franz N, Gilbert E, Grinter C, Gonzalez VH, Horsley P, Lee S, Maier C, Miko I, Morris P, Oboyski P, Pierce NE, Poelen J, Scott VL, Smith M, Talamas EJ, Tsutsui ND, Tucker E (2021) Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 5: e74037.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.5.74037>
14. Salim JA, Seltmann KC, Poelen JH, Saraiva AM (2022) Indexing Biotic Interactions in GBIF data. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 6: e93565.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.6.93565>

Talks/Posters:

1. Seltmann, KC. (2021) New TCN: Big-Bee. Virtual ADBC Summit. Presentation for iDigBio and the ADBC program. Retrieved from https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/ADBC_Summit_2021 on 21 Sept 2021
2. Seltmann, K.; Allen, J.; Brown, B. V.; Carper, A.; Engel, M. S; Franz, N., et al. (2021) Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards*, 5(e74037). Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0937b5gp>
3. Gonzalez, VH., Seltmann, KC., Brown, B., Allen, J., Carper, A., Engel, M., et al. (2021) Big-Bee: Una iniciativa para promover el conocimiento de las abejas a través de la digitalización de imágenes y datos de rasgos. ID 112. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0856h3d2>. Poster from XII Congreso Mesoamericano de Abejas Nativas, Centro de Investigaciones Apícolas Tropicales (CINAT), Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica, Nov. 20-21, 2021. The poster is in Spanish.
4. Thrift, C. N, & Seltmann, K. C. (2021) Identifying island-mainland bee populations with wings. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/4h46m0ws>
5. Eisner de Eisenhof, L., & Seltmann, K. (2022) Body Size and Taxonomic Influence on Bee Wing Vein Density. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0z73n6vt>
6. Xu, C., & Seltmann, K. C. (2022) Variation of Ocelli Size Between Male and Female Bees in Species of Different Sociality. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0v065150>

7. Wong-Lau, J., Klauke, H., Kaur, H., Alexander, N., Bang, J., & Seltmann, K. C. (2022) Big-Bee: Hair Recognition and Quantification. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0fb1n3pw>
8. Miller, J. T, & Seltmann, K. C. (2022) Environmental Trends in the Distribution of California Bee Species. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/36w6x8pp>
9. Seltmann KC, Allen J, Brown BV, Carper A, Eldredge T, Engel MS, Franz N, Gilbert E, Grinter C, Gonzalez VH, Horsley P, Kung GA, Lee S, Maier C, Miko I, Morris P, Oboyski P, Ostwald MM, Pierce NE, Poelen J, Scott VL, Smith C, Smith M, Talamas EJ, Tsutsui ND, Tucker E. (2022) Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. International Union for the Study of Social Insects (IUSSI), San Diego, CA.
10. Allen, J. (2022) Notes from Nature: Goals, Accomplishments and Future Directions. WeDigBio Oct 14th Virtual
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15. Seltmann K.C., Miller J.T. & Poelen J.H. (2022) Global bee interaction database. Entomological Society of America. Vancouver, BC, Canada. November 2022.
16. Seltmann KC, Allen J, Brown BV, Carper A, Eldredge T, Engel MS, Franz N, Gilbert E, Grinter C, Gonzalez VH, Horsley P, Kung GA, Lee S, Maier C, Miko I, Morris P, Oboyski P, Ostwald MM, Pierce NE, Poelen J, Scott VL, Smith C, Smith M, Talamas EJ, Tsutsui ND, Tucker E. (2022) Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. Entomological Society of America. Vancouver, BC, Canada. Poster. November 2022.
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19. Poelen, J. (2023) Bee Species Interactions. Native Bee Monitoring RCN Data Management Workshop. Zoom. Talk. March 2023
20. Jorrit Poelen (2023) was presented virtually at NanoSessions #1 #2 on 2023-02-28/2023-03-28 titled "How Big is That Bee" to help facilitate the publication of Big-Bee specimens and traits in semantically Nanopublications. Organized by KnowledgePixel (<https://knowledgepixels.com/>) and attended by Pensoft Publishers (<https://pensoft.net>) among others. See <https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network/UCSB-IZC00012194/blob/main/nanosessions-presentation-2023-02-28.md> and <https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network/UCSB-IZC00012194/blob/main/nanosessions-presentation-2023-03-28.md> for text-based slides
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24. Miller, JT. Exploring shared life-history strategies as a driver for biodiversity in desert bees & plants. (2023) Digital Data, June 5-7, 2023
25. Seltmann, KC. (2023) New and Current TCNs: Parasite Tracker and Big-Bee. Entomological Collection Managers Workshop, July 19, 2023
26. Smith, C., K. C. Seltmann. (2023) You're it: tagging specimen images in Symbiota to facilitate their use in research. Society for the Preservation of Natural History Collections Annual Meeting, San Francisco, CA. June 1, 2023.
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31. Cervantes Rivera, L., Radwich, R., Ostwald, M. M, & Seltmann, K. C. (2024). Identifying the Impact of Body Measurements on Dry Weight Across and Within Bee Species. *UC*

- Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/1dp4h100>
32. Radwich, R. M, Cervantes Rivera, L., Ostwald, M. M, & Seltmann, K. C. (2024). Variation in Bee Body Size Due to Anthropogenic Land Use. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/841173cj>
 33. Rink, J.; Kavuluru, R.; Golich, D.; Moon, P.; Rajagopal, N.; Huang, J., et al. (2024). Bee Species Identification: Improving Population Monitoring Techniques . *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/7z6734gt>
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 35. Bonnet, N. H, Ostwald, M. M, & Seltmann, K. C. (2024). Physiological Traits as Predictors of Climate Resistance and Sociality in Female Carpenter Bees. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/31x6m4nc>
 36. You, T., Ostwald, M., & Seltmann, K. (2024). Striped Ambiguity: A Quantitative Approach Towards Understanding Camouflage Using Computer Vision. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/8xd7s974>

Websites and Data Portals:

Big-Bee project website: <http://big-bee.net>

Bee Library Symbiota Portal: <https://library.big-bee.net>

Big-Bee focused Global Biotic Interactions project page:

<https://www.globalbioticinteractions.org/bigbee>

iDigBio Wiki:

[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php?title=TCN: Extending Anthophila research through image and trait digitization \(Big-Bee\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php?title=TCN:_Extending_Anthophila_research_through_image_and_trait_digitization_(Big-Bee))

Big-Bee Network GitHub Project: <https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network>

YouTube (Macroscopic Solutions): <https://macroscopicsolutions.com/video-tutorial-big-bee-tcn;>

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXhbJ-JirA3-J7FihjXtUyg>

Notes from Nature Big-Bee Bonanza project:

<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/md68135/notes-from-nature-big-bee-bonanza>

Other Publications (Datasets and Reports):

1. The full proposal can be found at Seltmann, K. C. (2021) Extending Anthophila research through image and trait digitization (Big-Bee) proposal. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/2vm761mv>

2. Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration, University of California Santa Barbara. (2021) UC Santa Barbara Invertebrate Zoology Collection (UCSB-IZC) Data Archive and Biodiversity Dataset Graph (0.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5557670>. Data publication that includes full UCSB Invertebrate Zoology Collection image corpus.
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4. Seltmann, Katja C., & Poelen, Jorrit H. (2022) Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.2.2) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5915003> on 28 Jan 2022
5. Katja C. Seltmann, & Global Biotic Interaction Community. (2022) Global Bee Interaction Data (v2.02) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6564718>
6. Seltmann, Katja C., Poelen, Jorrit H., Engel, Michael, & Gonzalez, Victor. (2022) Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.3.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5915012> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5915012> on 28 Jan 2022
7. Seltmann, Katja C., Poelen, Jorrit H., Allen, Julie, Eldredge, Taro, Engel, Michael, & Gonzalez, Victor. (2022) Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.4.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6950082>
8. Publications of Big-Bee Images: Big-Bee Community, Poelen, Jorrit H., & Seltmann, Katja. (2022) *Xylocopa sonorina* - UCSB-IZC00012194 - Bee Library - 73e389aa-5886-4c48-8778-ba8932d1bd7e
hash://sha256/96bfde1efa599e0e8e61de18b14d61dd308737f684950e4079c04e9bc0f33958 hash://md5/4940f68c84cffa4412f7ffb98bb255bd (0.0.3) [Data set]. Zenodo. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7114665.
9. Seltmann, Katja, Poelen, Jorrit H., UCSB Natural History Collections, & Big-Bee Community. (2023) *Halictus ligatus* Halictidae UCSB-IZC00036803 <https://library.big-bee.net/portal/collections/individual/index.php?occid=72096> Male - Bee Library - 73e389aa-5886-4c48-8778-ba8932d1bd7e
hash://sha256/3a178bd2f588c35eb9729309d1baa769ea819bcd5bb5142c2de208dd8e299d1a hash://md5/88a7c9b9b2df777a17e707aab635b3ef [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7510912> .
10. Miller, JT, Poelen, Jorrit, & Seltmann, Katja. (2023) Big-Bee Name Alignment Workshop. Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.7829969.
11. Seltmann, Katja C., Poelen, Jorrit H., Allen, Julie, Eldredge, K. Taro, Engel, Michael, Gonzalez, Victor, Knowles, L. Lacey, & Horsley, Pam. (2023) Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.7.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7865367
12. Brianne Du Clos, Julien Brun, Sam Droege, Jen Hammock, Andrew Johnston, Jonathan Koch, Clare Maffei, Cynthia Sims Parr, Jorrit H. Poelen, Katja C. Seltmann, & Erika M. Tucker. (2023) US National Native Bee Monitoring RCN Data Management Workshop: Public Domain Videos (1.0.0). Zenodo. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7868217.

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14. Seltmann, K. C., Poelen, J. H., & Global Biotic Interaction Community. (2024). Global Bee Interaction Data (v4.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12639658>
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16. Seltmann, K. C., Poelen, J. H., Allen, J., Eldredge, K. T., Engel, M., Gonzalez, V., Knowles, L. L., & Horsley, P. (2023). Big Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.8.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8184843>
17. Poelen, JH (ed .) . (2024). Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources hash://sha256/83617875e84bb8ae7ac2a257ad50eb8e82d8935d975f465b8ee8f3a803f72b48 hash://md5/c639d7e3fcd5603f6c48e9d5e6c49672 (0.24) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11105453>
18. José Augusto Salim, & Jorrit Poelen. (2024). globalbioticinteractions/nomer: 0.5.13 (0.5.13). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.1145474>
19. Seltmann, K., & Poelen, J. (2024). Tab and comma delimited versions of Discover Life bee species guide and world checklist (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Anthophila) (56.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10019874>
20. Smith, C., Reyes, S., Ryan, K. A., Smith, M., Deer, E., Sanchez, E., Sheccid, R. T., Kung, G.-A., Carper, A. L., & Seltmann, K. (2024). UCSB's 3D imaging and modeling protocol. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10594883>
21. Seltmann, K. (2024). Exhibit at California Nature Art Museum, San Luis Obispo, CA: the The Birds and the Bees and More: Pollinators hash://md5/4f552ae78473131eafb39657f95c6260. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10612006>

Other Products (Non-scholarly Articles):

1. Shelly Leachman (2021). Creating a Buzz. UCSB Current. Retrieved from <https://www.news.ucsb.edu/2021/020448/creating-buzz> on 27 Oct 2021.
2. Tara Duggan. (2021). To help fight the loss of bees, the California Academy of Sciences to share a 180,000-strong collection online. San Francisco Chronicle. Retrieved from <https://www.sfchronicle.com/climate/article/To-help-fight-loss-of-bees-California-Academy-of-16570034.php> on 2 Nov 2021.
3. Matt Kettmann. Bee Happy. UC Santa Barbara Magazine Retrieved from <https://magazine.ucsb.edu/spring-summer-2022/bee-happy> on July 25, 2022.

Participants

13 institutions are funded by the Big-Bee project (Table 5). Lead participants and institution codes are listed below from each institution. A total of 107 people worked on the Big-Bee project, including PIs, collection managers, students, volunteers, technicians, and postdoctoral scholars (Table 6). 37 undergraduate students received some financial compensation for the project, and 17 students received course credit. 2 graduate students and 2 postdoctoral scholars contributed to the project. These numbers do not include complete statistics for UMMZ, who did not report their participant numbers in time to create the cumulative annual report.

UCMC PI Carper accepted a position as Senior Ecologist in the Climate Initiatives Department at the City of Boulder. He will continue administering the award and oversee digitization activities through his Entomology Curator Adjoint appointment at CU Boulder. Given delays from renovations and the database transition, we received a no cost extension to extend the award period though August 31 2025. Michael Engel (University of Kansas) and Brian Brown (Natural History Museum, Los Angeles County) both retired. Brian Brown was replaced by Jody Martin as PI of Big-Bee. Victor Gonzalez-Betancourt (co-PI) took over the PI role at University of Kansas. This will be the last year with UNR PI Julie Allen as they did not request a NCE for next year and they have completed the requirements for the grant.

Institution	Institution Code	Participant	Institution affiliation
Arizona State University	ASUHIC	Nico Franz	School of Life Sciences, Hasbrouck Insect Collection
		Ed Gilbert	School of Life Sciences
		Sangmi Lee	Hasbrouck Insect Collection
California Academy of Sciences	CAS	Chris Grinter	California Academy of Sciences, Entomology
Florida State Collection of Arthropods	FSCA	Elijah Talamas	Florida Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services, Division of Plant Industry
Harvard University	MCZ	Naomi Pierce	Department of Organismic and Evolutionary Biology, Museum of Comparative Zoology
		Crystal Maier	Museum of Comparative Zoology, Entomology
Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County	LACM	Jody Martin	Natural History Museum, Los Angeles County, Entomology
		Giar-Ann Kung	Natural History Museum, Los Angeles County, Entomology

San Diego Natural History Museum		Pamela Horsley	San Diego Natural History Museum, Entomology
University of California-Berkeley	EMEC	Neil Tsutsui	Department of Environmental Science, Policy and Management
		Peter Oboyski	Essig Museum of Entomology
University of California, Santa Barbara	UCSB	Katja C Seltmann	Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration, Earth Research Institute
University of Colorado, Boulder	UCMC	Adrian Carper	Museum of Natural History, Entomology
		Virginia Scott	Museum of Natural History, Entomology
		Victor Gonzalez-Betancourt	Department of Natural Sciences and Mathematics - Ecology & Evolutionary Biology, KU Biodiversity Institute
University of Michigan Museum of Zoology	UMMZ	L. Lacey Knowles	University of Michigan Museum of Zoology Insect Collection
		Taro Eldredge	University of Michigan Museum of Zoology Insect Collection
University of Nevada, Reno	UNR	Julie Allen	Department of Biology
University of New Hampshire	UNHC	Istvan Miko	Donald S. Chandler Entomological Collection

Table 5: List of project PIs and lead participants at each Big-Bee funded institution.

	UNH C	UMM ZI	UCS B	FSC A	UNR	SEM C	SDM C	UCM C	CAS	EME C	LACM	ASUHI C	MCZ	Total
Undergraduate students hired (i.e., paid)	6	0	12	0	0	2	0	2	0	9	0	3	3	37
Undergraduate students working for course credit	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	17
Undergraduate student volunteers	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	7
Non-student volunteers	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	8	1	0	0	0	12
Total number of undergraduate students	6	2	27	2	0	2	0	2	0	13	0	7	3	64
Graduate students	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2

	UNH C	UMM ZI	UCS B	FSC A	UNR	SEM C	SDM C	UCM C	CAS	EME C	LACM	ASUHI C	MCZ	Total
Non-student staff	1	2	3	2	2	1	3	2	3	2	4	2	3	30
Total number of people	8	4	30	4	2	4	5	4	11	16	4	9	6	108

Table 6: Number of people involved in Big-Bee during 23-24.

Partner Organizations

- Notes from Nature
- US National Native Bee Monitoring RCN
- iDigBio
- Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG)
- Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU)
- USGS Native Bee Inventory and Monitoring Lab
- Macroscopic Solutions, LLC

Other Collaborators

Erika Tucker - Terrestrial Parasite Tracker Digitization Taxonomy Manager, Milwaukee Public Museum; Research Associate, Biodiversity Outreach Network (BON); iDigBees

Hollis Woodard - Assistant Professor, University of California - Riverside; PI USDA US National Native Bee Monitoring RCN (<https://www.usnativebees.com>)

Elizabeth Hill - Agricultural Research Service, US Department of Agriculture

Andrew Johnson - Invertebrate Collections Manager - NEON Biorepository, Arizona State University, Symbiota Support Hub

Andrew Johnston - Formerly ASU, Neon Biorepository, Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU); Presently Purdue University

Katie Pearson - Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU); CAP TCN

Lindsay Walker - Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU)

Thomas van de Kamp - Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Laboratory for Applications of Synchrotron Radiation

Robert Guralnick - Curator of Biodiversity Informatics, Florida Museum of Natural History, University of Florida, iDigBio, Notes from Nature

Impacts

What is the impact on the development of the principal discipline(s) of the project?

With GloBI consultant Jorrit Poelen, Big-Bee is demonstrating a distributed system of sharing image and specimen records using linked data using hash technology. The data sharing methodology could facilitate dataset sharing that more accurately keeps track of data provenance. Records and images from the Bee Library are also shared as citable data publications through the Internet Archive and Zenodo. These published archives have a digital identifier (DOI) and an identifier that verifiably identifies the archive content (hash). The archives include metadata describing the origin of the specimen records and images and the records and images themselves. An example of an early published image corpus is available at:

- Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration, University of California Santa Barbara. (2021). UC Santa Barbara Invertebrate Zoology Collection (UCSB-IZC) Data Archive and Biodiversity Dataset Graph (0.2) [Data set]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5660088>
<https://archive.org/details/preston-ucsb-izchash://sha256/d5eb492d3e0304afadcc85f968de1e23042479ad670a5819cee00f2c2c277f36>
 -
- Big-Bee Community, Poelen, Jorrit H., & Seltmann, Katja. (2022) *Xylocopa sonora* - UCSB-IZC00012194 - Bee Library - 73e389aa-5886-4c48-8778-ba8932d1bd7e hash://sha256/96bfde1efa599e0e8e61de18b14d61dd308737f684950e4079c04e9bc0f33958 hash://md5/4940f68c84cfa4412f7ffb98bb255bd (0.0.3) [Data set]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.71146651>

Big-Bee continues to play an active role in the US Bee Monitoring Research Coordination Network, contributing a specimen-based perspective to ecological research and emphasizing the significance of voucher specimens and collections. Additionally, PI Seltmann, along with collaborators Elizabeth Hill, Hollis Woodard, Erika Tucker, and others, are developing the Wild Bee Standard, a Darwin Core standard for sharing bee monitoring data. This standard emerged from a comprehensive two-day workshop focused on biodiversity data for Bee Monitoring Network participants.

What is the impact on other disciplines?

Big-Bee continues to seek partners for developing artificial intelligence and improved 3D modeling applications using Big-Bee images. Seltmann mentored students from UCSB Statistics and Applied Probability Department for a Data Science Capstone in all three years of the project. In 2023 the capstone focused on methods for quantification of wing venation in bees to assess bee health (through fluctuating asymmetry) and automated identification of bees through wing veins (Figure 3). The impact includes focused training in conservation issues for future data science professionals.

1. Rink, J.; Kavuluru, R.; Golich, D.; Moon, P.; Rajagopal, N.; Huang, J., et al. (2024). Bee Species Identification: Improving Population Monitoring Techniques . UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/7z6734gt>

Figure 3: Visualization of a landmark decision tree for bee species identification.

Big-Bee continues to promote the sharing of images under Creative Commons 0/Public Domain licenses, which already has received attention from MediaWiki and computer vision bee identification initiatives (Brian Spiesman - <https://beemachine.ai>; Automated Wildlife Monitoring - <https://automated-wildlife-cig.github.io>) that are actively searching for open images of bees. Open access to images is also an important impact in the realm of technology transfer.

Big-Bee efforts in image sharing and data reporting led to the improvement of existing open tools like Preston, Nomer, and Elton (see <https://jhpoelen.nl> for more info) to the benefit of other publicly funded projects such as “*Intelligently predicting viral spillover risks from bats and other wild mammals*” (NIH R21 Grant 1R21AI164268-01 - <https://reporter.nih.gov/project-details/10289637>), “*Towards the Web of Biodiversity Knowledge: Understanding Data Connectedness to Improve Identifier Practices*” (NSF OAC 1839201 - https://www.nsf.gov/awardsearch/showAward?AWD_ID=1839201), “*Digitizing collections to trace parasite-host associations and predict the spread of vector-borne disease - Parasite Tracker TCN*” (NSF DBI:1901932 - https://www.nsf.gov/awardsearch/showAward?AWD_ID=1901932). A resulting publication that uses Big-Bee data and benefited from the software updates is Elliott, M.J., Poelen, J.H. & Fortes, J.A.B. Signing data citations enables data verification and citation persistence. *Sci Data* 10, 419 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02230-y>

Figure 4: Demographic breakdown of Big-Bee participants based on an anonymous self-reporting survey developed by LACM and UCSB.

What is the impact on the development of human resources?

In our proposal, we committed to recruiting participants from underserved communities using existing programs already found at the collaborating institutions. To track these metrics, Big-Bee created a DEI survey for our annual report. The survey is based on a survey used for the CAP TCN that includes groups defined as underrepresented in Science and Engineering (<https://www.nsf.gov/statistics/2017/nsf17310/digest/introduction>). **107** people were part of this project in the third year. **62%** of the Big-Bee participants are gender minorities in science and engineering (Women, Trans people, etc.), and **15%** are people of color/ racial and ethnic minority groups in science and engineering (Black or African American, Hispanic, Indigenous). **30%** self-described as Asian, and **53%** as White (Figure 4). 82 of the 107 project participants completed the survey and are included in these statistics. The percentage of our reporting participants from minority groups in science and engineering remains consistent with last year.

This year, UCSB awarded two paid, full-time internships for students identified by the UCSB Office of Education Partnerships, Smithsonian Scholars program. The interns participated in imaging bees and working with Notes from Nature. The Office of Education Partnerships' mission is to increase college-going rates for low-income students and/or students who will be the first in their families to pursue higher education.

What is the impact on teaching and education experiences?

The collaborative efforts of Big-Bee and its committed team of educators, researchers, and mentors have paved the way for a thriving environment that encourages undergraduate participation in research and fosters the development of future biodiversity experts and

collection managers. Undergraduate students make up a large proportion of the workforce in university collections. Big-Bee has already demonstrated a commitment to training the next generation of collection managers and biodiversity researchers about the use and importance of natural history collections. Big-Bee institutions hired **37** undergraduate students, **17** participated for course credit and **7** as volunteers. The students gave **1** oral presentation about Big-Bee and **10** posters. These numbers are fairly consistent with last year. There were **11** undergraduate research projects across the Big-Bee network. Among these projects, 8 were conducted at UCSB, where the 2 project postdoctoral scholars worked. The presence of these postdoctoral scholars has been instrumental in providing mentorship and guidance in undergraduate research initiatives.

Figure 5: Images from education and teaching experiences across the Big-Bee network. The image on the right is from the 38th annual Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County Bug Fair where Entomology technicians greeted over 10,000 visitors (and spelled BUGS with their arms). Image left is a UCSB undergraduate presenting at the Ecological Society of America Meeting in Long Beach, California.

All institutions created value-added activities for undergraduates, staff, and the public (Figure 5), including:

- We are collectively adding to the Macroscopic Solutions forum about imaging and 3D modeling <https://macroscopicsolutions.com/forum/official-forum/>
- UCSB has two full-time paid first-generation transfer students in summer 2024 working on Big Bee imaging. They participated in a series of Carpentries data science and introduction to programming offerings from the UCSB Library, an undergraduate STEM conference at UCSB, and resume/career counseling activities.

- Seltmann and UCSB postdoc Maddie Ostwald co-mentored a Statistics and Probability Department capstone course focused on extraction and evaluation of wing venation from bee images. The students developed a bee identification app from wings and explored other methods for classifying morphotypes based on supervised and unsupervised clustering methods. This is potentially transformative as it could provide quantitative methods for sorting bees to morphotype, thus improving ecological studies.
- ASUHIC delivered presentations on the diversity of insects, emphasizing bees as critical pollinators, to an ASU BIO 410 class, to biology students at Seton Catholic Preparatory High School, Arizona, and to 9th-grade students at Westwood High School, Arizona.
- EMEC hosted tours of the collection for ~475 UC Berkeley students from various classes and the local community, including a demonstration of their digitization workflow and tours for 550 people during Alumni / Homecoming weekend and “Darwin Day.”
- EMEC and the UC Berkeley Urban Bee Lab hosted a two-day workshop on California’s Native Bees at the UC Hopland Research and Extension Center for 25 students, and EMEC displayed California bees at the “Pollinator and Friends Day” at the Ruth Bancroft Garden in Walnut Creek, California to over 500 visitors.
- EMEC hosted a reception for an Annual IPM Advisors Retreat where they discussed the importance of natural history collections and digitized data for improving early pest detection, monitoring, and rapid response.
- SDNHM hosted UCSD PhD candidate Jess Mullins and Patricia Simpson for a “Nat Talk” about native pollinators. Pam Horsley, Christiana Mojica, and Taylor Hori tabled the event, sharing pinned specimens and images from the BigBee project.
- SDMC participant Deer trained SDNHM Summer STEM Apprentice, Chelsea Eckhart on imaging system, bee identification, and curation.
- At MCZ, co-PI Maier and project participant Zoe Flores spoke about the Big-Bee project and the importance of collection digitization to museum-goers at two Harvard Museum of Natural History insect-themed events, which reached 300 museum visitors, and gave 4 behind-the-scenes tours to local college courses with ca. 120 participants total.
- To date, the MCZC has trained 13 undergraduate student interns and one high school student on digitization and entomology collections procedures.

What is the impact on physical resources that form infrastructure?

UCSB was funded to purchase a micro-CT from USDA NIFA (GRANT14138107) titled “Micro-CT visualization of bees and their nests to investigate drivers of pollinator declines”. This award was largely based on the success of Big-Bee and continuing the investigations into morphological variation in bees as induced by environmental change.

What is the impact on institutional resources that form infrastructure?

Nothing to report.

What is the impact on information resources that form infrastructure?

Nothing to report.

What is the impact on technology transfer?

The Macropod PRO 3D is a portable focus stacking and 3D photogrammetry system capable of capturing high resolution images of samples >2 microns and 3D models >500 microns. Largely attributed to Macropod orders and referrals by Big-Bee, Agisoft and Mitutoyo have onboarded Macroscopic Solutions as an official distributor of Metashape and Mitutoyo's precision product line. The relationship enables widespread price reductions for Macroscopic Solutions systems and offers customers an increased range of imaging and measurement capabilities.

The speed of capture and computer processing of 3D models from focus stacked imagery has increased as new settings were implemented to accommodate wider focal planes resulting from aperture values between f8.0-16.0. These figures will be shared in upcoming manuscripts describing the photogrammetric methods used for Big-Bee. Similar methods are to be used in cooperation with USAFA and SpaceForce for the Polaris Dawn mission tentatively scheduled for July 15th (<https://polarisprogram.com>). Macroscopic Solutions has provided 4 Macropod PRO 3D imaging systems to 3D model *Arabidopsis* roots grown in space. When the samples return to Earth, they are to be immediately photographed and modeled prior to gene sequencing. We have created a method to capture data for 3D photogrammetry in under 6 minutes and 30 seconds.

Other notable adaptations of the Macropod have been enhanced to capture detailed images of insect and soil trays, herbarium specimens and larger materials requiring digitization. In June 2024, Macroscopic Solutions submitted pitch number 00083723 to the America's Seed Fund NSF SBIR-STTR to hire a team to build the next generation imaging and microscopy system designed to substantially increase 3D photogrammetry and focus stacking, which would have implications reaching far outside academic research and may serve as the pinnacle color scanning technology in industry for objects ranging from 0.5 microns to 10 cm in size.

Our portal is managed by the Symbiota Support Hub (ASU & iDigBio), which hosts the majority of the Symbiota portals at this time. We are building off of the trait module started from the CAP TCN and the interactions with Global Biotic Interactions originally initiated by the Tri-Tropic TCN and further developed during the Parasite Tracker TCN. Symbiota users can also access developments and innovations during the Big-Bee project through our GitHub repository.

Members of iDigBees are participating in our Slack, and we plan to share data between the two projects. MCZ is also instrumental to the NSF-funded "LightningBug" project, which aims to develop an imaging system that captures images of specimens and their labels in 3-D, to reconstruct the labels in a flat, computer-readable form. MZC will connect efforts and aid in exchanging ideas between Big-Bee and LightningBug.

What is the impact on society beyond science and technology?

One of the largest impacts of the project is our commitment to increasing awareness about bees and other insects in our communities. This comes through outreach events, including support for Xerces Society conservation initiatives such as the Bee Campus program (UCB & UCSB), pollinator gardens, or bug-themed museum events. A total of **15,260** people attended Big-Bee related events. A few examples from this year include:

- At LACM, Sylvia Reyes and Kate Ryan participated in two museum outreach events, Earth Day Festival and Bug Fair with slides showcasing the project, and visitors participated in the Notes from Nature Big-Bee Bonanza! expeditions (11,000 visitors).
- ASUHC showcased insect diversity, including pollinators, at the ASU Open Door on the ASU Tempe campus and the Spring Butterfly Festival in Scottsdale, AZ.
- UCMC - co-PI Carper took museum drawers of specimens, as well as tablets with pre-loaded 3D models of bees to the Boulder Bee Festival, where he and a team from the museum interacted with over 200 children and families.
- SEMC hosted “Hasta Luego Monarchs” at the Pollinator Prairie in Olathe, Kansas for about 500 primary and secondary students from the Kansas City area.
- PI Grinter gave tours for the Development department at CAS to a pair of trustees particularly interested in bees and bee digitization.
- At MCZ, co-PI Maier has set up a collaboration with the Harvard beekeeping club, with plans to lead a tour for Beekeeping Club members and a crowdsourcing event.
- EMEC participated in a Pollinator Garden project as part of a Xerces Society “Bee Campus” where students plant and manage native California plants in a pollinator demonstration garden on the UC Berkeley campus.
- LACM Adventures in Nature summer camp students were given a tour of the Big-Bee lab and 3D imaging setup.
- SDNHM staff gave a behind the scenes tour for bee enthusiasts and volunteers working at Torrey Pines State Natural Reserve to document native bees using iNaturalist; Multiple summer camp groups and high school students were given behind the scenes tours of Entomology collection and the Big-Bee Project was highlighted.
- Seltmann (under Irene Moon) finished a 11 week radio piece called Antenna Alley on WFMU radio being aired Mondays at 10PM EST during the [Daniel Blumin show](#). The segments are factual, but with music contributed by a series of internationally recognized artists including GX Jupiter-Larsen, Ian MacPhee, LoVid, Ironing, Ergo Phizmiz and Lottie Bowater, The Virus, Francisco López, Hearty White, Jana Winderen, Wobbly, Matmos, Rose, venoztk & People Like Us. WFMU is a free-form, New York based radio station that archives its shows and streams online. It has a very wide international audience and is highly regarded for its programming. WFMU has a very wide, global listenership.

What percentage of the award's budget was spent in a foreign country?

Nothing to report.

Changes/Problems

We have nothing to report for changes in approach, expenditure impact, care of human subjects, care of vertebrate animals, or changes in the use of biohazards. A few institutions had setbacks this year. UCMC had a major water leak that stopped imaging in the collections for most of 2024. LACM's collection underwent significant renovations that stopped image production for several months. FSCA/SDMC lost critical employees and had to hire/retrain someone new. See individual collaborator reports for more details about these setbacks and how each institution is planning to stay on target.

Actual or Anticipated problems or delays and actions or plans to resolve them:

The Canon DSLR cameras used for 3D imaging in this project are subjected to intense use, resulting in error 20 and 30 codes on camera bodies, which are typically caused by shutter failures due to the high volume of images required for 3D photogrammetry—approximately 2,000 to 8,000 images per specimen. Repairs for these cameras generally take around 10 days, but project downtime has been minimized thanks to the prompt support from Macroscopic Solutions, which frequently provides loaner cameras or flashes during the repair process. This issue is ongoing and has prompted considerations for future imaging systems, including the adoption of mirrorless cameras.